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Assessing The Social and Environmental Justice of Compensation Mechanisms For Road Infrastructure Projects in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the effectiveness of compensation mechanisms in the context of the Bida Ring Road project in Niger State, Nigeria. The research investigates the adequacy, timeliness, and transparency of compensation payments, as well as their impact on project timelines and social equity. Through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, interviews, and document analysis, the study assesses the experiences of affected landowners and communities. The findings reveal significant shortcomings in the compensation process, including inadequate compensation amounts, delays in payment, and a lack of transparency. These issues have led to social unrest, legal challenges, and project delays. The study concludes by emphasizing the need for more equitable and sustainable compensation practices to ensure the successful implementation of road infrastructure projects in Nigeria. Recommendations are provided to improve the compensation process, including strengthening legal frameworks, enhancing transparency, and involving affected communities in decision-making.

Keywords: Social Justice, Environmental Justice and Mixed-methods Approach

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Road infrastructure plays a vital role in economic development by facilitating trade, transportation, and communication (Abdulazeez, Magaji & Musa, 2022). In developing countries like Nigeria, the need for sustainable road infrastructure is critical. However, challenges such as compensation for land acquisition and resettlement often impede timely project delivery. Sustainable compensation extends beyond financial obligations; it encompasses ethical, social, and environmental responsibilities that directly influence the success and longevity of infrastructure projects. This study investigates the effectiveness of sustainable compensation payment, using the Bida Ring Road project in Niger State as a case study.

Nigeria, with its expansive landmass and dense population, requires a robust road network to support its development goals (Agbadagbe, Musa & Ismail, 2024). While the government has launched numerous road projects aimed at enhancing connectivity and economic growth (Oladimeji & Lawal,

2020), these initiatives frequently suffer from delays, cost overruns, and even abandonment. A key contributor to these setbacks is the contentious issue of land compensation (Adamu & Danladi, 2019). Although the Land Use Act of 1978 permits the government to acquire land for public purposes, it mandates compensation to affected persons (Amadi & Nwosu, 2020), yet the process is often fraught with inefficiencies.

The legal framework, mainly derived from the Land Use Act, lacks specificity in determining compensation amounts, resulting in varied practices across states (Nigerian Law Reform Commission, 2021; Akpan & Udo, 2019). To address these inconsistencies, recent reforms such as the National Infrastructure Policy of 2020 aim to standardize the valuation and payment processes (Federal Ministry of Works, 2020). However, implementation remains slow and inconsistent, raising concerns about the policy's effectiveness (Magaji, Gurowa & Abubakar, 2014).

The Bida Ring Road project, initiated in 2019, illustrates these compensation challenges vividly. Many landowners reported that the compensation offered did not reflect the true value of their land and properties, and delays in payment sparked protests and legal battles (Mohammed et al., 2021). Furthermore, the process lacked transparency, with allegations of misappropriation of funds and inadequate communication from government officials (Akinwale & Ogunbiyi, 2021). These disputes significantly disrupted project timelines and construction progress.

Efforts by the Niger State government to engage with stakeholders have helped address some concerns, yet the experience underscores the necessity for more effective compensation strategies (Niger State Ministry of Works, 2021). Fair, timely, and transparent compensation reduces conflict, enhances community cooperation, and promotes sustainable project delivery (Onyema & Eze, 2020; Babalola et al., 2021). Moreover, it fosters trust and long-term success by aligning development goals with social equity (Magaji, Musa & Ismail, 2025; Ogunleye & Ajayi, 2020). Ultimately, the study calls for stronger policies and mechanisms to institutionalize sustainable compensation in Nigeria's infrastructure sector.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Social Justice

Social justice in compensation mechanisms for road infrastructure projects focuses on ensuring fair treatment for affected communities by providing equitable compensation for lost land, homes, and livelihoods. This involves addressing the fair distribution of benefits and burdens, especially for marginalized groups, to prevent them from bearing disproportionate impacts. In projects like the Bida Ring Road in Niger State, social justice assesses how well compensation mechanisms protect the rights of affected individuals and communities, considering both monetary and non-economic losses such as displacement and disruption to social networks. An effective approach also includes ensuring the timely and appropriate compensation, such as resettlement assistance or livelihood restoration programs, to help communities rebuild their lives and maintain social stability, ultimately contributing to long-term social justice (Gyamfi, 2021; Alhassan & Ibrahim, 2020).

2.1.2 Environmental Justice

Environmental justice in road infrastructure projects ensures that the environmental burdens, such as pollution, habitat destruction, and biodiversity loss, are fairly distributed, particularly avoiding disproportionate impacts on marginalized communities. In the case of the Bida Ring Road, this involves assessing how well compensation mechanisms address environmental damage, such as ecosystem destruction and the degradation of local resources vital to community livelihoods. It also requires considering long-term environmental consequences like soil erosion and pollution, ensuring these risks are mitigated. To achieve environmental justice, compensation should include sustainable approaches that focus on ecological restoration, long-term resource preservation, and participatory processes where affected communities can influence environmental mitigation strategies. By integrating these principles, compensation mechanisms align with broader goals of sustainable development and community well-being (Elder, 2020; Reed, 2019).

2.2. Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Social Justice Theory

Social Justice Theory, particularly as articulated by John Rawls (1971), focuses on fairness and equality, emphasizing the just distribution of resources and opportunities, with special consideration for the disadvantaged. In the context of compensation for road infrastructure projects, this theory advocates that those displaced should be compensated not only to restore their pre-displacement status but also to avoid bearing an unfair share of the project's costs (Olawuyi, 2015). Rawls' "difference principle" suggests that inequalities can only be justified if they benefit the least advantaged, which aligns with the need for compensation that improves or at least maintains the living standards of affected individuals. Fair compensation, according to Social Justice Theory, should reflect the full scope of losses, including the financial, social, and psychological impacts of displacement, such as the loss of community ties and traditional livelihoods (Ogunwusi, 2019). Moreover, Social Justice Theory emphasizes redistribution and the restoration of rights, advocating for compensation practices that support the relocation, livelihood restoration, and access to essential services for displaced individuals (Amadi et al., 2020). In many Nigerian infrastructure projects, however, financial compensation often fails to address these broader social and economic effects, underscoring the need for more comprehensive approaches (Olatunji, 2018).

2.3. Empirical Review

Popoola et al. (2024) investigate the impact of compulsory acquisition and compensation processes on the satisfaction of urban fringe residents in Abuja, focusing on Gwagwalada Area Council. Employing a survey research design and simple random sampling, data were collected and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study revealed that while residents found procedures such as notice of possession and compensation disbursement somewhat effective, there was overall dissatisfaction, largely due to inadequate compensation and a lack of transparency in the process. To improve resident satisfaction, the authors recommended enhancing transparency and ensuring fair and adequate compensation during land acquisition procedures.

Abubakar, Magaji and Ismail (2025) examine the satisfaction levels of individuals displaced by the Bida Ring Road project in Niger State, Nigeria, with a focus on the fairness, transparency, and adequacy of the compensation process. Drawing on survey data from 347 affected landowners, the research reveals a mixed response: while many were informed about payment timelines, concerns remain over the fairness and adequacy of compensation, particularly regarding asset valuation, livelihood restoration, and hidden costs. The findings highlight persistent challenges in delivering equitable compensation in Nigerian infrastructure projects and emphasize the need for improved valuation methods, greater transparency, stakeholder engagement, timely payments, and effective grievance mechanisms. The study offers valuable insights into the factors shaping satisfaction with compensation and suggests strategies for more just and sustainable practices in future developments.

Oshikoya and Olayiwola (2023) assess claimants' satisfaction with the land acquisition and compensation process in Ona-Ara Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. Using a purposive sampling technique, the researchers selected 186 respondents and gathered data through structured questionnaires, which were analyzed with descriptive statistics, including frequency tables, mean scores, and the Relative Satisfaction Index (RSI). The findings indicated that while claimants expressed satisfaction with aspects such as their involvement in decision-making, timeliness of procedures, and communication channels, they were dissatisfied with delays in compensation payments, inaccurate enumeration of assets, and a lack of transparency. The study recommended improvements in transparency, accurate asset assessment, and prompt compensation payments to enhance overall satisfaction with the process.

Abubakar, Magaji and Ismail (2025) examine the specific gaps and challenges in the compensation process for the Bida Ring Road project in Niger State, Nigeria. Drawing on empirical evidence from a mixed-methods study, the research identifies key shortcomings in compensation adequacy, timeliness, and transparency. These challenges have significant implications for the livelihoods of affected communities and the overall success of the road project. The study concludes by highlighting the need for reforms in policy and practice to ensure more equitable and efficient compensation processes in future infrastructure development initiatives.

Despite the growing body of literature examining land acquisition and compensation processes in Nigeria, including studies by Popoola et al. (2024), Abubakar, Magaji, and Ismail (2025), and Oshikoya and Olayiwola (2023), a significant research gap persists in the comparative and integrative analysis of compensation satisfaction across different geopolitical zones, project types, and community contexts. While individual studies highlight recurring issues such as inadequate compensation, lack of transparency, and flawed asset valuation, most focus on isolated case studies without exploring how local governance structures, socio-economic factors, or project scale influence these outcomes. Additionally, few studies have employed a mixed-methods approach that deeply integrates qualitative narratives of displaced persons with quantitative satisfaction indices to uncover nuanced experiences. This gap underscores the need for broader, multi-site research that not only captures regional variations but also proposes standardized frameworks for assessing and improving compensation practices across Nigeria.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

For this study, the survey research design was adopted. As Section One outlined, The study's objectives informed the design choice. This research design provides a quick, efficient, and accurate means of assessing information about a population of interest. It intends to study Assessment of Sustainable Compensation Payment on Road Infrastructural Delivery in Nigeria: A case study of Bida Ring Road in Niger State.

3.3 Study Area

The study is centered on the Bida Ring Road in Niger State, Nigeria. This road project is a major infrastructural initiative to enhance connectivity, reduce traffic congestion, and promote socio-economic development. Bida is a significant town in Niger State with a population engaged in both agricultural and commercial activities, making transportation infrastructure critical to its economic well-being. The road's development process has involved compensation payments to displaced individuals, landowners, and businesses, which is central to the study.

3.4 Population of the Study

The population for this study consists of individuals and groups directly or indirectly involved in the Bida Ring Road project in Niger State, Nigeria. This includes Project Affected Persons (PAPs), such as landowners, residents, and business owners who were displaced or impacted by the road construction and were eligible for compensation. Additionally, government officials responsible for administering compensation payments and overseeing the road project are key to the population. These officials are drawn from relevant agencies such as the Niger State Ministry of Works and the Ministry of Lands.

Furthermore, contractors and consultants engaged in the construction and management of the Bida Ring Road are included in the population. These professionals play a critical role in delivering the road infrastructure, and their perspectives on how compensation payments affect project timelines and quality will provide valuable insights. Lastly, the local community members, including leaders, traders, and residents who use the road or are otherwise impacted by its construction, form part of the study population. Their experiences and perceptions of the road infrastructure delivery process are essential for understanding the broader socio-economic impact of the project on the community. A total of 2600 is the population figure from which the sample size was determined.

3.5 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The researcher used Taro Yamane's formula to determine the sample size of the population. Taro Yamane's formula is given as.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where N = Population of study (2600)

n = Sample size (?)

e = Level of significance at 5% (0.05)

1 = Constant

∴

$$n = \frac{2600}{1 + 2600(0.05)^2} = \frac{2600}{1+2600(0.0025)} = \frac{2600}{1+6.5}$$

$$n = \frac{2600}{7.5} = 346.6 = 347$$

The sample size, therefore, is 347 respondents.

3.6 Research Instrument and Instrumentation

Data for this study was collected from primary and secondary sources. The primary source of data collected was mainly the use of a structured questionnaire which was designed to elicit information on the Assessment of Sustainable Compensation Payment on Road Infrastructural Delivery in Nigeria: A case study of Bida Ring Road in Niger State. The secondary sources of data collection were textbooks, journals, and scholarly materials.

3.7 Validity of Instrument

The instrument of this study was subjected to face validation. Face validation tests the appropriateness of the questionnaire items. Face validation often indicates whether an instrument on a face appears to measure what it contains. Face validations, therefore, aim at determining the extent to which the questionnaire is relevant to the study's objectives. In subjecting the instrument to face validation, copies of the initial draft of the questionnaire will be validated by the supervisor. The supervisor is expected to critically examine the instrument's items with specific objectives of the study and make valuable suggestions to improve the quality of the instrument. Based on his recommendations, the instrument will be adjusted and re-adjusted before being administered for the study.

3.8 Reliability of Instrument

The coefficient of 0.81 was considered a reliability coefficient because, according to Etuk (1990), the test-retest coefficient of 0.5 will be enough to justify using a research instrument.

3.9 Method of Data Collection

This study utilizes two main sources of data: primary and secondary. The primary data comprises raw information collected directly from respondents through structured questionnaires and interviews, providing firsthand insights relevant to the research objectives. In contrast, the secondary data is derived from a comprehensive review of existing literature, including journals, monographs, textbooks, and other scholarly publications, which offer background information and support for the study's theoretical framework.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected will be analyzed using a frequency table, percentage, and mean score analysis. In contrast, the nonparametric statistical test (Chi-square) was used to test the formulated hypothesis using SPSS (statistical package for social sciences). Haven gathered the data by administering a questionnaire; the collected data will be coded, tabulated, and analyzed using SPSS statistical software according to the research question and hypothesis. To effectively analyze the data collected for easy management and accuracy, the chi-square method will be used to test independence. The Chi-square is given as:

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum (o-e)^2}{e}$$

Where X^2 = Chi-square
 o = observed frequency
 e = expected frequency

Level of confidence/degree of freedom

When employing the Chi-square test, a certain confidence level or margin of error must be assumed. Moreover, the degree of freedom in the table must be determined in a simple variable, row, and column distribution; the degree of freedom is $df = (r-1)(c-1)$

Where df = degree of freedom

r = number of rows

c = number of columns.

In determining the critical chi _ square value, the confidence value is assumed to be at 95% or 0.95. A margin of 5% or 0.05 is allowed for judgment error.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

The research will adhere strictly to ethical guidelines to safeguard the rights and well-being of the participants. Informed consent will be obtained from all respondents before participating in the study. Confidentiality will be maintained by anonymizing the collected data, ensuring that individual responses cannot be traced back to specific participants. Furthermore, participants will be assured that their involvement is voluntary and that they can withdraw from the study without facing any consequences. The research will respect privacy, autonomy, and dignity throughout data collection.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULT

The data gathered were presented according to the order in which they were arranged in the research questions. Simple percentages were used to analyze the demographic information of the respondents, while the chi-square test was adopted to test the research hypothesis.

4.1 Analysis Of Demographic Data Of Respondents

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	216	62.0	62.0
	Female	131	37.7	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 1 above shows the gender distribution of the respondents used for this study. Out of the total number of 347 respondents, 216 respondents which represent 62.0 percent of the population are male. 131 which represent 37.7 percent of the population are female.

Table 2: Age range of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30years	81	23.3	23.3
	31-40years	121	35.1	58.4
	41-50years	90	25.6	74.0
	Above 50 years	55	16.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 2 above shows the age grade of the respondents used for this study. Out of the total number of 347 respondents, 81, representing 23.3 percent of the population, are between 20 and 30 years old. 121, representing 35.1 percent of the population, are between 31 and 40 years old. 90, representing 25.6 percent of the population, are between 41 and 50 years old. 55, representing 16.0 percent of the population, are above 50 years old.

Table 3: Educational Background of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	FSLC	69	20.0	20.0
	WASSCE/GCE/NECO	87	25.0	45.0
	OND/HND/BSC	122	35.0	80.0
	MSC/PGD/PHD	52	15.0	95.0
	OTHERS	17	5.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 3 above shows the educational background of the respondents used for this study. Out of the total number of 347 respondents, 69, representing 20.0 percent of the population, are FSLC holders. 87, representing 25.0 percent of the population, are SSCE/GCE/WASSCE holders. 122, representing 35.0 percent of the population, are OND/HND/BSC holders. 52, representing 15.0 percent of the population, are MSC/PGD/PHD holders. 17, representing 5.0 percent of the population, had other types of educational qualifications.

Table 4: Marital Status

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	104	30.0	30.0
	Married	191	55.0	45.0
	Divorced	17	5.0	65.0
	Widowed	35	10.0	80.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 4 above shows the marital status of the respondents used for this study. 104, representing 30.0 percent of the population, are single. 191, representing 55.0 percent of the population, are married. 17, representing 5.0 percent of the population, are divorced. 35, representing 10.0 percent of the population, are widowed.

4.3 Analysis of Psychographic Data

Table 5: Believe the amount of compensation paid was fair compared to the value of the land or property lost

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	130	37.0	37.0
	Agree	142	41.0	78.0
	Undecided	30	9.0	87.0
	Disagree	14	4.0	91.0
	Strongly disagree	31	9.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 5 shows respondents' responses if the amount of compensation paid was fair compared to the value of the land or property lost. 130 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, strongly agreed that the amount of compensation paid was fair compared to the value of the land or property lost. One hundred forty-two respondents, representing 41.0 percent, agreed that the compensation paid was fair compared to the value of the lost land or property. Thirty respondents, representing 9.0 percent, were undecided. 14 respondents, representing 4.0 percent, disagreed that the compensation paid was fair compared to the value of the land or property lost. Thirty-one respondents, representing 9.0 percent, strongly disagreed that the compensation paid was fair compared to the value of the land or property lost.

Table 6: The compensation sufficient to enable the affected persons to relocate or reinvest elsewhere

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	102	29.0	29.0
	Agree	128	37.0	66.0
	Undecided	18	5.0	71.0
	Disagree	57	16.0	87.0
	Strongly disagree	42	13.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 6 shows the respondents' responses to whether compensation is sufficient to enable the affected persons to relocate or reinvest elsewhere. 102 respondents, representing 29.0 percent, strongly agree that the compensation is sufficient to enable the affected persons to relocate or reinvest elsewhere. 128 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, agree that the compensation is sufficient to enable the affected persons to relocate or reinvest elsewhere. Eighteen of the respondents, representing 5.0 percent, were undecided. 57 respondents, representing 16.0 percent, disagree that the compensation is sufficient to enable the affected persons to relocate or reinvest elsewhere. 42 respondents, representing 13.0 percent, strongly disagree that the compensation is sufficient to enable the affected persons to relocate or reinvest elsewhere.

Table 7: There were hidden costs or expenses you had to bear not covered by the compensation

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	137	39.0	39.0
	Agree	125	36.0	75.0
	Undecided	45	13.0	88.0
	Disagree	40	12.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 7 shows respondents' responses if the compensation did not cover hidden costs or expenses they had to bear. 137 respondents, representing 39.0 percent, strongly agree that the compensation did not cover hidden costs or expenses they had to bear. 125 respondents, representing 36.0 percent, agreed that the compensation did not cover hidden costs or expenses. 45 of them, representing 13.0 percent, were undecided. 40 of the respondents, representing 12.0 percent, disagree that there were hidden costs or expenses not covered by the compensation.

Table 8: The compensation payment was adequate to maintain the previous standard of living after the displacement

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	102	29.0	29.0
	Agree	128	37.0	66.0
	Undecided	18	5.0	71.0
	Disagree	57	16.0	87.0
	Strongly disagree	42	13.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 8 shows the respondents' responses to whether the compensation payment was adequate to maintain the previous standard of living after displacement. 102 of the respondents, representing 29.0 percent, strongly agree that the compensation payment was adequate to maintain the previous standard of living after displacement. 128 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, agree that the compensation payment was adequate to maintain the previous standard of living after displacement. 18 of the respondents, representing 5.0 percent, were undecided. 57 respondents, representing 16.0 percent, disagree that the compensation payment was adequate to maintain the previous standard of living after displacement. 42 of the respondents, representing 13.0 percent, strongly disagree that the compensation payment was adequate to maintain the previous standard of living after displacement.

Table 9: Alternative compensation options (such as land-for-land or housing) were offered in addition to financial compensation

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	130	37.0	37.0
	Agree	142	41.0	78.0
	Undecided	30	9.0	87.0
	Disagree	14	4.0	91.0
	Strongly disagree	31	9.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 9 shows respondents' responses to whether alternative compensation options (such as land-for-land or housing) were offered in addition to financial compensation. 130 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, strongly agreed that alternative compensation options (such as land-for-land or housing) were offered in addition to financial compensation. 142 respondents, representing 41.0 percent, agreed that alternative compensation options (such as land-for-land or housing) were offered in addition to financial compensation. Thirty respondents, representing 9.0 percent, were undecided. Fourteen respondents, representing 4.0 percent, disagreed that alternative compensation options (such as land-for-land or housing) were offered in addition to financial compensation. 31 respondents, representing 9.0 percent, strongly disagreed that alternative compensation options (such as land-for-land or housing) were offered in addition to financial compensation.

Table 10: Informed in advance about when the compensation payment would be made

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	205	59.0	59.0
	Agree	97	28.0	87.0
	Disagree	35	10.0	97.0
	Strongly disagree	10	3.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 10 shows respondents' responses if they were informed about when the compensation payment would be made. 205 respondents, representing 59.0 percent, strongly agree that they were informed when the compensation payment would be made. 97 respondents, representing 28.0 percent, agree that they were informed about when the compensation payment would be made. 35 respondents, representing 10.0 percent, disagree that they were informed about when the compensation payment would be made. 10 respondents, representing 3.0 percent, strongly disagree that they were informed in advance about when the compensation payment would be made.

Table 11: The compensation payment arrived when it was promised

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	126	36.0	36.0
	Agree	97	28.0	64.0
	Undecided	19	6.0	70.0
	Disagree	45	13.0	83.0
	Strongly disagree	60	17.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 11 shows respondents' responses if the compensation payment arrived when promised. 126 respondents, representing 36.0 percent, strongly agree that the compensation payment arrived when promised. 97 respondents, representing 28.0 percent, agree that the compensation payment arrived when promised. 19 of them, representing 6.0 percent, were undecided. 45 respondents, representing 13.0 percent, disagree that the compensation payment arrived when promised. Sixty respondents, representing 17.0 percent, strongly disagree that the compensation payment arrived when promised.

Table 12: Aware of any delays in the construction of the road that were linked to compensation issues

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	134	39.0	39.0
	Agree	112	32.0	71.0
	Disagree	67	19.0	90.0
	Strongly disagree	34	10.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 12 shows the responses of respondents if they were aware of any delays in the construction of the road that were linked to compensation issues. 134 of the respondents, representing 39.0 percent, strongly agree that they were aware of any road construction delays that were linked to compensation issues. 112 of the respondents, representing 32.0 percent, agree that they were aware of any road construction delays that were linked to compensation issues. 67 of the respondents, representing 19.0 percent, disagree that they were aware of any road construction delays that were linked to compensation issues. 34 of the respondents, representing 10.0 percent, strongly disagree that they were aware of any road construction delays that were linked to compensation issues.

Table 13: The government or project managers offer explanations or justifications during delay of payments

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	102	29.0	29.0
	Agree	128	37.0	66.0
	Undecided	18	5.0	71.0
	Disagree	57	16.0	87.0
	Strongly disagree	42	13.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 13 shows respondents' responses if the government or project managers offer explanations or justifications during the delay of payments. 102 of the respondents, representing 29.0 percent, strongly agree that the government or project managers offered explanations or justifications during the delay of payments. 128 of the respondents, representing 37.0 percent, agree that the government or project managers offered explanations or justifications during the delay of payments. Eighteen of the respondents, representing 5.0 percent, were undecided. 57 respondents, representing 16.0 percent, disagree that the government or project managers offered explanations or justifications during the delay of payments. 42 of the respondents, representing 13.0 percent, strongly disagree that the government or project managers offered explanations or justifications during the delay of payments.

Table 14: There were clear communication channels for reporting delays in compensation payments

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	102	29.0	29.0
	Agree	128	37.0	66.0
	Undecided	18	5.0	71.0
	Disagree	57	16.0	87.0
	Strongly disagree	42	13.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 14 shows respondents' responses to whether there were clear communication channels for reporting delays in compensation payments. 102 respondents, representing 29.0 percent, strongly agree that there were clear communication channels for reporting delays in compensation payments. 128 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, agree that there were clear communication channels for reporting delays in compensation payments. Eighteen of the respondents, representing 5.0 percent, were undecided. 57 respondents, representing 16.0 percent, disagree that there were clear

communication channels for reporting delays in compensation payments. 42 respondents, representing 13.0 percent, strongly disagree that there were clear communication channels for reporting delays in compensation payments.

Table 15: Informed about the criteria used to determine the amount of compensation

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	130	37.0	37.0
	Agree	142	41.0	78.0
	Undecided	30	9.0	87.0
	Disagree	14	4.0	91.0
	Strongly disagree	31	9.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 15 shows respondents' responses if they were informed about the criteria used to determine the compensation amount. 130 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, strongly agreed that they were informed about the criteria used to determine the compensation amount. 142 respondents, representing 41.0 percent, agreed that they were informed about the criteria used to determine the compensation amount. Thirty respondents, representing 9.0 percent, were undecided. Fourteen respondents, representing 4.0 percent, disagreed that they were informed about the criteria used to determine the compensation amount. Thirty-one respondents, representing 9.0 percent, strongly disagreed that they were informed about the criteria used to determine the compensation amount.

Table 16: The authorities provide documentation or proof of how your compensation was calculated

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	70	20.0	20.0
	Agree	142	41.0	61.0
	Undecided	20	6.0	67.0
	Disagree	61	18.0	85.0
	Strongly disagree	48	15.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 16 shows respondents' responses if the authorities provide documentation or proof of how their compensation was calculated. Seventy respondents, representing 20.0 percent, strongly agreed that the authorities provide documentation or proof of how their compensation was calculated. 142 respondents, representing 41.0 percent, agreed that the authorities provided documentation or proof of how their compensation was calculated. Twenty respondents, representing 6.0 percent, were undecided. 61 respondents, representing 18.0 percent, disagreed that the authorities provide documentation or proof of how their compensation was calculated. 48 respondents, representing 15.0 percent, strongly disagreed that the authorities provide documentation or proof of how their compensation was calculated.

Table 17: Aware of the stakeholders involved in the decision-making process for compensation

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	102	29.0	29.0
	Agree	128	37.0	66.0
	Undecided	18	5.0	71.0
	Disagree	57	16.0	87.0
	Strongly disagree	42	13.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 17 shows respondents' responses if they know the stakeholders involved in the decision-making process for compensation. 102 of the respondents, representing 29.0 percent, strongly agree that they know the stakeholders involved in the decision-making process for compensation. 128 respondents, representing 37.0 percent, agree that they know the stakeholders involved in the decision-making process for compensation. Eighteen of the respondents, representing 5.0 percent, were undecided. 57 respondents, representing 16.0 percent, disagree that they know the stakeholders involved in the decision-making process for compensation. 42 of the respondents, representing 13.0 percent, strongly disagree that they know the stakeholders involved in the decision-making process for compensation.

Table 18: Feel that the compensation process was free from corruption or manipulation

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	70	20.0	20.0
	Agree	142	41.0	61.0
	Undecided	20	6.0	67.0
	Disagree	61	18.0	85.0
	Strongly disagree	48	15.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 18 shows the respondents' responses if the compensation process was free from corruption or manipulation. Seventy 20.0 percent of respondents strongly agreed that the compensation process was free from corruption or manipulation. 142 respondents, representing 41.0 percent, agreed that the compensation process was free from corruption or manipulation. Twenty respondents, representing 6.0 percent, were undecided. 61 respondents, representing 18.0 percent, disagreed that the compensation process was free from corruption or manipulation. 48 respondents, representing 15.0 percent, strongly disagreed that the compensation process was free from corruption or manipulation.

Table 19: An independent body or third-party group was overseeing the compensation process

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	126	36.0	36.0
	Agree	97	28.0	64.0
	Undecided	19	6.0	70.0
	Disagree	45	13.0	83.0
	Strongly disagree	60	17.0	100.0
	Total	347	100.0	

Source: Field Survey.

Table 19 shows respondents' responses if an independent body or third-party group oversaw the compensation process. 126 respondents, representing 36.0 percent, strongly agree that an independent body or third-party group oversaw the compensation process. 97 respondents, representing 28.0 percent, agree that an independent body or third-party group was overseeing the compensation process. 19 of them, representing 6.0 percent, were undecided. Forty-five of the respondents, representing 13.0 percent, disagree that an independent body or third-party group was overseeing the compensation process. Sixty of the respondents, representing 17.0 percent, strongly disagreed that an independent body or third-party group was overseeing the compensation process.

4. 4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The evaluation of compensation practices for the Bida Ring Road project revealed a combination of satisfaction and significant concerns among affected persons. While 78% of respondents expressed contentment with the fairness of compensation, a considerable number highlighted issues related to transparency, insufficient compensation amounts, and delays in disbursement. Many participants (42%) strongly disagreed that the compensation provided was adequate for relocation or reinvestment, and 87% reported not being informed of how compensation amounts were determined. In addition, 83% criticized the lack of communication from government officials regarding payment delays, suggesting that the process lacked transparency and proper stakeholder engagement.

The findings further underscored key systemic challenges in Nigeria's compensation system for infrastructure projects. Inadequate compensation that fails to reflect market value, along with neglect for non-financial impacts such as loss of livelihoods and cultural disruptions, often fuels dissatisfaction and resistance from affected communities. Payment delays compound these issues, resulting in disruption of livelihoods and delays in project execution. Such inefficiencies increase project costs and create avoidable conflicts between stakeholders, thereby hindering smooth infrastructure development.

Moreover, the research highlighted broader structural issues including lack of transparency, corruption, and an outdated legal framework governing compensation. Communities are often uninformed about compensation procedures, which fosters mistrust and resentment. Current practices focus narrowly on financial restitution without addressing social, environmental, and livelihood restoration needs. Additionally, the legal and institutional mechanisms—especially the outdated Land Use Act of 1978—lack the necessary provisions and enforcement capacity to ensure fair and effective compensation. Addressing these challenges requires reforming legal policies, improving institutional capacity, ensuring inclusive stakeholder engagement, and developing holistic compensation strategies that consider both financial and non-financial losses.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study underscores the importance of effective and equitable compensation mechanisms in the successful delivery of road infrastructure projects, using the Bida Ring Road project as a case study. The research revealed critical gaps in compensation practices, such as insufficient payments, delays, and lack of transparency, which led to financial strain, social unrest, and project delays. To address these challenges, the study recommends strengthening legal and institutional frameworks, establishing independent and transparent valuation processes, and ensuring timely compensation disbursement. It also advocates for greater stakeholder engagement and the adoption of a holistic approach that accounts for both financial and socio-environmental impacts. Implementing these strategies can foster trust, reduce conflict, and promote sustainable infrastructure development in Nigeria and other developing nations.

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